

Management of energy and tension of magnetic field of systems of magnetically-impulsive processing components in automated mode

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Abstract. The systems of the magnetically-impulsive strengthening of hardware are considered in the article. The method of management the high-energy systems is offered that allows to change energy and tension of magnetic-field depending on good that is processed So as an enormous amount of the existent systems of magnetically-impulsive treatment limit in a sphere uses by the sizes of concrete details. The use of the system with adjusting of energy of impulse and tension of magnetic-field allows extending to possibility of the use of the system.

Key words: Magnetically-impulsive treatment, solenoid, penetration of magnetic-field in a metal, strengthening of metals.

Introduction. The problem of increasing of operational reliability of details is complex and assumes using of modern methods of strengthening treatment. The most important part of this problem is to improve the material properties of the surface layer of details, including through the use of inexpensive, environmentally friendly and effective methods of strengthening.

Research actuality. Realization of modern magnetically-impulsive technologies assumes the non-permanent power operating on the processed object with amplitude sufficient for the required level of his deformation. The general significant drawback of existing magnetically-impulsive generators of power is that their work is based on the single impulse of the power operating under permanent power permanent and unchanging tension of magnetic-field. It limits technological possibilities of executable operations, as a result, considerably restricts their scope.

Setting objectives of the study: Rationalization of method of management of magnetic-field tension and by energy of impulse for the systems of magnetically-impulsive treatment of wares.

Exposition of basic material: System of magnetically-impulsive treatment – is a device that uses magnetic energy as a working fluid. There are varieties of the systems of magnetic treatment depending on destination: for straightening, malfunction and strengthening of structure and other. There are many varieties of the systems of magnetically-impulsive treatment. For example:

1. Method of magnetically-impulsive treatment of the thin-walled metals by the unipolar impulses of current. Patent of Ukraine for invention №76485.
2. Devices are for magnetically-impulsive treatment. Patent of the Russian federation № RU2068327.
3. Method of the magnetically-impulsive attracting of the thin-walled sheet-metals lotcoins circular induction inductor system. Patent of Ukraine for useful model №92037.
4. Pat. US 2008/0163661 A1 USA (CIIA). Dent removing method and device [1].

The main disadvantage of these systems is the constancy of the magnetic field and energy of impulse that narrows the scope of applicability.

By the reserve of energy of impulse distinguish low-power systems in which arrester connected through a diode bridge and transistor power outlet without accumulating circuit and high energy impulse which is formed by accumulating charge circuit with capacitors.

Management is reduced the first to determination of the opening time of the transistor, that in turn controls the time of impulse, time of pause and number of impulses in general implementation of the scheme is possible on a microcontroller. Limitations of these systems due by the power supply capacity [2].

High energy magnetic treatment systems unlike a little energy work due to the charge of condenser and direct it to surge.

Tension of magnetic-field on the axis of the solenoid is calculated by the formula:

$$H = \frac{n \cdot I}{2} \cdot (\cos \alpha_2 - \cos \alpha_1) , \text{ A/M} \quad (1)$$

Where I – the current in the solenoid coil in amperes

n – a number of coils on a 1m of length of solenoid

α_1 and α_2 – angles under that the radiuses of butt ends of solenoid are visible from

a point A on the axis where tension of magnetic-field is determined (Pic.1).

From Pic.1 is clear that to the point 0 in the center of the solenoid $\alpha_1 = 180^\circ - \alpha_2$ and $\cos\alpha_1 = -\cos\alpha_2$

The magnetic field in the center of the solenoid is defined as:

$$H = n \cdot I \cdot \cos\alpha_2 \quad (2)$$

Picture 1. The geometry of the solenoid

If the length of the solenoid is much more than its diameter and magnetic material is not used, then at flowing of current through the winding inside the coil a magnetic field directed along the axis is created which is uniform and constant current equal in magnitude [3]:

$$B = \mu_0 n I \quad (3)$$

$$B = \frac{4\pi}{c} n I \quad (4)$$

where μ_0 – permeance of vacuum, $n = \frac{N}{l}$ – a number of coils on length of solenoid unit, N – a number of coils, I – a current in a puttee.

By virtue of that two halves of infinite solenoid in the point of their connection makes the same contribution to the magnetic field, magnetic induction of semi-infinite solenoid at its edge twice less than in the bulk. The same can be said about the field on edges eventual, but rather a long solenoid [4]:

$$B_{KP} = \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 n I \quad (5)$$

At flowing of current a solenoid stocks energy equal to the work that must be done for establishment of current supply. The value of this energy is equal to:

$$E_{\square} = \frac{\psi I}{2} = \frac{LI}{2} \quad (6)$$

where $\psi = N \Phi$ – flux linkage, Φ – magnetic flux in the solenoid, L – inductance of the solenoid.

At the change of current in the solenoid EMF induction occurs, the value of which is:

$$\varepsilon = -L \frac{dI}{dt} \quad (7)$$

Inductance of solenoid is expressed thus:

$$L = \mu_0 n^2 V \frac{\mu_0 z^2}{4\pi l} \quad (8)$$

$$L = 4\pi n^2 V \frac{z^2}{l} \quad (9)$$

where μ_0 – permeance of vacuum, $n = \frac{N}{l}$ – a number of coils on length of solenoid unit, N – a number of coils, V – volume of solenoid, $z = \pi d N$ – length of the explorer wound on the solenoid, l – length of solenoid, d – diameter of coil.

Without the use of magnetic material magnetic induction within the limits of solenoid is actually constant and equal

$$B = \mu_0 \frac{NI}{l} = \mu_0 nI \quad (10)$$

where I – strength of current.

Ignoring edge effects at the ends of the solenoid will get that flux through the coil magnetic induction equally multiplied by the cross-sectional area and the number of turns:

$$\psi = BSN = \mu_0 N^2 \frac{IS}{l} = \mu_0 nVI = LI \quad (11)$$

From here a formula follows for inductance of solenoid equivalent to the formulas 10 and 11.

$$L = \mu_0 \frac{N^2 S}{l} = \mu_0 n^2 V \quad (12)$$

It follows from these formulas that if to change strength of current and number of turns independently of each other, you can change the intensity and energy of the magnetic field also independently. Therefore, we developed an automatic magnetic-impulse processing of metal products in which the field tension and power are adjusted in the necessary details.

Based on the formulas of the magnetic field can be changed by changing the power supply or the number of turns. And changing energy flux or magnetic flux, as the current strength affects the intensity and energy of the change in current strength cannot control distribution. So the system has to change the number of turns, which is achieved using multiplanimetric solenoid and the permeability of the material that is achieved by introducing a ferromagnetic rods using solenoid or solenoid plate with a change in cross-sectional area.

Conclusions: The results of calculations above experimental magnetic pulse installation was made that allows multiple work mode bit pulse repetition to load and change the momentum and energy of the magnetic field. The system is built to MCU, enabling high performance and automation process.

Thus control system magnetic pulse of details that allows you to change the momentum and energy magnetic field of the solenoid, which significantly extend the range of influence of magnetic treatment in detail. This modification allows the system to make the system universal regardless of size, weight or material product system can be adjusted by changed the program in the microcontroller.

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